

An updated checklist of Psychidae (Lepidoptera) of Albania

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Abstract: The last checklist of Psychidae given in Arnscheid & Weidlich (2017) has been updated. Altogether 23 species of Psychidae are confirmed for the territory of Albania. *Eochorica balcanica* is excluded from the list, and *Psyche casta* and *Reisseronia pusilella* were found as new for the country during the field studies. New records for ten species are provided in the present study.

Keywords: Albania, faunistics, Psychidae

Introduction

Psychidae had always been poorly studied in the Balkans as majority of Microlepidoptera. First data concern records of Hans Rebel and his collaborators (Rebel, 1913, 1917, 1918, 1931). Just recently it received more attention by Psychidae specialist Michael Weidlich, who published results from his own study (Weidlich, 2013b) in Albania. There are several publications that follow, however there are only a few records each in those papers: Weidlich (2012, 2013a), Arnscheid & Weidlich (2017), Nahirić & Beshkov, (2017), Beshkov, Plant & Nahirić (2020) and Arnscheid (2024). This checklist was done as a part of an initiative for updating data on Microlepidoptera of Albania, supported by recent lepidopterological studies in Albania (see Plant et al., 2025).

Material and methods

Field trips in Albania were conducted from 2016–2024. Specimens were collected by light traps, an entomological net or reared. The collecting methods involved 2 portable light traps with an 8 watt “Blacklight” white tube (368 nm) and 8 watt “Blacklight” black tube, both powered by 12 volt 9 Ah batteries, as well as a Finnish “tent trap” with a

160 watt MV bulb at the top of the pole and a 20 watt (368 nm) black light lamp over the catching pot below, powered by a generator. An additional 20 watt (368 nm) lamp was also positioned about 70–90 m from the tent trap. The distance between the Finnish “tent trap” and the light traps, as well as between the light traps themselves, was sometimes several hundred metres, as they were deployed with different outlooks wherever possible. All traps ran throughout the night. From the second half of August 2022 onwards the Finnish “tent trap” was furnished with LepiLED, 1.5 maxi model UV LED lamp with adapter and transformer 220 – 12 V, powered by a generator. Dissection of genitalia was done according to Robinson (1975). All genitalia were preserved in micro vials filled with glycerol. Specimens were deposited in the collection of the author in National Museum of Natural History in Sofia (NMNHS). All specimens were collected by Ana Nahirić-Beshkova and Stoyan Beshkov.

Results

The checklist is based on a list given in Arnscheid & Weidlich (2017). There are confirmed records for 23 Psychidae species in Albania. *Eochorica balcanica* is excluded from the list. *Psyche casta* and *Reisseronia pusilella* are reported for the first time in the present

paper. *Psyche casta* is not a rare species in the Balkans and its founding in Albania was expected, while *Reisseronia pusilella* is Balkan endemic present in neighbouring countries of North Macedonia and Greece, as well as in Bulgaria (Arnscheid & Weidlich, 2017). Of all 23 species 20 are recorded since 2008. *Diplodoma laichartingella* is recorded in 1961 only, while *Montanima predotae* and *Psychidea nudella* are recorded only in 1918. New records for ten species are provided in the present study.

Eumasia parietariella (Heydenreich, 1851)

Literature data: Bicaj, 1918; Kukës, Kula e Lumës, 1918, (Rebel & Zerny, 1931); Vlorë, Borsh, 1961 (Petersen, 1964), Gjirokastró, 2006; Malësia i Lunxhërisë, Dragot, 2008; Bzhjetë-Skhrel, 2008; Zuri, 2010; Gjegjan, 2010; Bënjë-Novoselë, 2012; Vau-Deja, 2013 (Weidlich, 2013b), Dragot, 2008 (Arnscheid, 2024).

Diplodoma laichartingella (Goeze, 1783)

Literature data: Vlorë, Borsh, 1961 (Petersen, 1964).

Taleporia tubulosa (Retzius, 1783)

Literature data: Kukës, Kuka e Lumës, 1918 (Rebel & Zerny, 1931), Balldren, 2008; Bzhjetë-Kurora e Lohes, 2008; Bogë, 920–1050 m NN, 2013 (Weidlich, 2013b).

New data: Korçë, Morava Mt above Dishnica, 1564 m, 25.06.2017, 2 males; Maja e Manjolave below, 1139 m, 20.06.2023, 2 males.

Typhonia melana (Frivaldszky, 1837)

Literature data: Dibër, Korab, 1918; Schkodër, Vermosh, Korab, 1918 (Rebel & Zerny, 1931), Petran, 2008 (Weidlich, 2013b).

Penestoglossa dardoinella (Millière, 1863)

Literature data: Berat, Vukopoles River Gorge, 2016 (Nahirnić & Beshkov, 2017), Ossumi River Canyon,

Çorovodë surrounding, opposite Çerenisht Village, 419 m (Beshkov, Plant & Nahirnić, 2020).

Psyche casta (Pallas, 1767)

New data: Pogradec, below Maja Ahishtes Geges, 1320 m, 18.06.2024, 1 male; Dajti Mt, Shkalle Village, 885 m, 8.06.2018, 1 male; Maja e Manjolave below, 1139 m, 20.06.2023, 1 male; Moravë Mt, between Dardhë and Boboshtica, 1240 m, 9.07.2016, 1 male.

Psyche crassiorella (Bruand, 1851)

Literature data: Shkodër, 1905 (Rebel, 1913); “Nordalbanien”, 1914 (Rebel, 1917); Kula e Lumës, 1918; Shkodër, 1918 (Rebel & Zerny, 1931), Borshi, 1961; Gjirokastró, 2006; Germenji, 2008; Gracen, 2008; Balldren, 2008, 2012; Bzhjetë-Skhrel, 2008; Bzhjetë-Kurora e Lohes, 2008; Bogë- Bridashës, 1.550 m NN, 2008; Gjegjan, 2010; Mullet, 2010; Shkodër S, 2011; Qafë Qelë, 2011, 2013; Gomsiqe Epërme, 2011; Kçirë, 2011; Fushë Arrëz, 2011; Fuzhë Krujë, 2012; Maminas, 2012; Rubjek, 2012; Memaliaj, 2012, Bënjë-Novoselë, 2012; Bogë vicinity, 920-1.050 m NN, 2013; Vau-Deja, 2013; Lajthizë, 2013; Kalimash, 2013 (Weidlich, 2013b).

New data: Lake Prespa, between Tren and Shuec villages, 860 m, 13.06.2024, e.p. 16.06.2024, 1 female.

Luffia lapidella (Goeze, 1783)

Literature data: Mullet, 2010 (Weidlich, 2013b).

Epichnopterix hellenidensis Weidlich, 2013

Literature data: Provinz Kolonje, Leskovik W, Radova 1 km S, 600 m, 2008; Malesia i Lunxherise. Dragot E, Vjoses-Tal, 150 m, 2008 (Weidlich, 2013a), Dragot, 2008 (Arnscheid, 2024).

New data: Osum River Canyon across Çerenisht Village, 390 m, 5.05.2022, 9 males, flying on road verge at 10:00–11:00 o'clock. Two cases were found, too (Fig. 1). Habitat is maquis with *Phyllirea latifolia*, *Arbutus unedo*, *Pistacia terebinthus*, *Quercus ilex*,

Figs 1–2. 1 – Larval case of *Epichnopterix hellenidensis* Weidlich, 2013 in 2 – Osum River Canyon across Çerenisht Village.

Fig. 3. Habitat of *Epichnopterix hellenidensis* Weidlich, 2013 in Osum River Canyon across Çerenisht Village. Maquis with *Phyllirea latifolia*, *Arbutus unedo*, *Pistacia terebinthus*, *Quercus ilex*, *Quercus* sp., *Paliurus spina-christi*, *Cotinus coggygia*, *Juniperus oxycedrus*, *Carpinus orientalis*, etc.

Quercus sp., *Palliurus spina-christi*, *Cotinus coggygria*, *Juniperus oxycedrus*, *Carpinus orientalis*, etc. (Figs 2–3). This species is Balkan endemic and known only from two localities in Greece and three localities in Albania.

Bijugis bombycella (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)

Literature data: Kula e Lumës, 1918, leg Predota (Rebel & Zerny, 1931), Vrisera, 2006, Radova, 2008 (Arnscheid & Weidlich, 2017).

New data: Dajti Mt, Shkalle Village, 885 m, 30.06.2017, 3 males; Maja e Manjolave below, 1139 m, 20.06.2023, 1 male.

Reisseronia pusilella (Rebel, 1940)

New data: Lake Prespa, between Tren and Shuec villages, 860 m, 13.06.2024, 1 male.

Heliopsycheidea graecella (Millière, 1866)

Literature data: Pojani, 1918 (Rebel & Zerny, 1931); Vrisera, 2006, Radova, 2008 (Arnscheid & Weidlich, 2017).

Montanima predotae Sieder, 1949

Literature data: Djalica e Lumës, 1918; Bështriq, 1918 (Rebel & Zerny, 1931).

Rebelia perlucidella (Bruand, 1853)

Literature data: Shkodër, 1918; Tirana, 1918 (Rebel & Zerny, 1931), Iba, 1961 (Weidlich, 2013b).

New data: Pogradec, below Maja Ahishtes Geges, 1320 m, 28.05.2023, 1 male; Qafa e Mollës Pass 674 m, 7.05.2022, 1 male.

Psychidea nudella (Ochsenheimer, 1810)

Literature data: Kruma, 1918 (Rebel & Zerny, 1931).

Stichobasis helicinoides (Heylaerts, 1879)

Literature data: Leskovik N, Gozharazhde E, 900 m, 2008, 2012 (Weidlich, 2012), Gozharazhde, 2008, 2012 (Weidlich, 2013b).

Canephora hirsuta (Poda, 1761)

Literature data: North Albania 1914 (Rebel, 1917), Kruma, 1918; Mamuras, 1918 (Rebel & Zerny, 1931), Poliçan, 1961; Mullet, 2010; Udënisht, 2010; Cangonj, 2010; Bogë vicinity, 1050 m NN, 2013; Bzhetë-Kurora e Lohes, 2013; Kalimash, 2013 (Weidlich, 2013b).

Pachythelia villosella (Ochsenheimer, 1810)

Literature data: Paša/Pasha liman, 1908 (Rebel, 1913); Kula e Lumës, 1918; Durrës, 1917 (Rebel & Zerny, 1931); Kunora e Lurës, 1961; Goranxi, 2006; Mt Dembei, Dragot, 2008; Petran, 2008; Radova, 2008, 2012; Shales, 2008; Floq, 2008; Gracen, 2008; Balldren, 2008, 2012; Bezhetë- Skhrel, 2008; Mjedë, 2010; Librazhd, 7 km W, 2010; Librazhd, SE, 2010; Shkodër S, 2011; Qafë Qelë, 2011; Kçirë, 2011; Fushë Arrëz, 2011; Paçram, 2012; Prezë, 2012; Maminas, 2012; Rubjek, 2012; Durrës, 2012; Rogozhinë, 2012; Lushnjë, 2012; Kolonjë, 2012; Mbrostar, 2012; Visokë, 2012; Greshicë, 2012; Dames, 2012; Bzhetë SW, 2013; Lajthizë, 2013 (Weidlich, 2013b), Shkodër env., Mjede 3 km E, 2010 (Arnscheid & Weidlich, 2017), Dragot, 2008 (Arnscheid, 2024).

New data: Cape of Rodon (= Kepi i Rodonit), Shetaj Village SW, 99 m, 23.05.2023, 1 male; Lushnja County, Ardenica Monastery vic., 124 m, 6.05.2022, 1 male.

Oiketicoides lutea (Staudinger, 1870)

Literature data: Megullë, 2011 (Weidlich, 2013b), Çajup, 2017 (Arnscheid, 2024).

New data: Çajup, 7.08.2018, 22 males; Çorogjafi Mt, Qafa e Selenicës, 8.08.2018, 7 males; Osum River Canyon, Çorovodë Town S, Çerenisht Village, 395 m, 9.08.2018, 5 males; Syri i Kaltër, 166 m,

6.08.2018, 1 male; Grammoz Mt, Borovë Village above, 1085 m, 21.07.2022, 1 male.

Ptilocephala plumifera (Ochsenheimer, 1810)

Literature data: Bështriq, 1918 (Rebel & Zerny, 1931), Bogë-Bridashës, 1400 m NN, 2008, leg. Weidlich (Weidlich, 2013b).

Megalophanes viciella (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775)

Literature data: Bështriq (Rebel & Zerny, 1931).
New data: Dajt Mt, Qafa e Mollës Pass, 674 m, 4.06.2019, 1 male.

Loebelia crassicornis (Staudinger, 1870)

Literature data: Durrës, 1917 (Rebel, 1918); Vrisera, 2006; Radova, 2008, 2012; Mullet, 2010 (Weidlich, 2012), Vrisera, 2006; Radova, 2008, 2012; Mullet, 2010; Visokë, 2012 (Weidlich, 2013b).

Apterona helicoidella (Vallot, 1827)

Literature data: Skutari-Brdica, 1905 (Rebel, 1913); Bështriq; Shkodra; Han i Grabom (Rebel & Zerny, 1931); Mt Dembei, Dragot, 2008; Germenji, 2008; Gozharazhde, 2008; Boboshticë, 2008; Grigan, 2008; Elbasan, 2008; Bzhetë-Skhrel, 2008; Mjedë, 2010; Librazhd SE, 2010; Udënisht, 2010; Plasë, 2010; Cangonj, 2010; Bilisht, 2010; Qafë Qelë, 2011; Fushë Arrëz, 2011; Visokë, 2012; Bogë, 920 m NN, 2013; Lajthizë, 2013 (Weidlich, 2013b), Dragot, 2008 (Arnscheid, 2024).

Excluded species

Eochorica balcanica (Rebel, 1919)

This species is erroneously included for Albania in Sauter & Hättenschwiler (1996), Sobczyk (2011), Weidlich & Arnscheid (2017) on the basis of records from North Macedonian part of Galičica Mt (= Mali i Thatë) published in Drenowski (1930).

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